

Utilization of fly ash and blast furnace slag for the preparation of mullite based composites

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Mullite based ceramics with ZrO_2 has been fabricated utilizing two important waste materials such as fly ash and blast furnace slag. With the dissociation of zircon upto 20% addition, sintering occurs within the region 1200–1300° and the developed thermochemical properties are significant.

Boccaccini *et al.*¹ obtained glass ceramics by controlled crystallization of vitrified incinerator filter fly ash. Hintzen *et al.*² prepared β -sialon powders from fly ash by a carbothermal reduction and nitridation process. Caligaris *et al.*³ studied the incorporation of waste materials in the production cycle as an interesting alternative in modern industry and the recycling of waste glass, electrical insulators and fly ash was studied. All the components obtained by uniaxial pressing of the powders, received thermal treatments. Shirakami *et al.*⁴ studied the heat treatment of two slags of different CaO content from municipal wastes. Boccaccini *et al.*⁵ used powder technology and sintering to transform a heavy metal containing vitrified municipal incinerator fly ash into glass-ceramics products. Kumar *et al.*⁶ formulated two cordierite compositions using raw and beneficiated fly ash together with calcined alumina and talc as starting materials.

The crystalline phase of fly ash varies with the coal-source and the temperature of firing. Similarly, the reactivity of blast furnace slag also depends on composition of the batch ingredients. The latter always offers a glassy phase at a moderate sintering temperature (1150–1200°). The existence of this glassy phase was utilized in incorporating ZrO_2 , a more refractory component in a blend of slag and fly ash, to fabricate a ZrO_2 -mullite composite. Sintering condition was adjusted according to the thermal interaction of both the ingredients.

The present investigation was undertaken to prepare a composite body out of the two waste materials such as fly ash and blast furnace slag, which may find various industrial applications.

Results and discussion

Fly ash, procured from the power station was very fine having surface area 70 m²/g. Chemical analyses of fly ash and slag (Table 1) indicate negligible amount of unburnt carbon. The mineralogical nature of the fly ash was ascertained by XRD pattern. The crystalline nature was evident and the phases identified were mullite as major along with quartz, haematite and magnetite. The basic object of the present investigation was to study the effect of ZrO_2 in a mixed body containing fly ash and slag (Table 2). The main constituents of the experimental slag were SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and CaO. The pellets and bars were fabricated by applying uniaxial pressure of 1000 kg/cm² in a hydraulic press.

Table 1. Chemical analysis of fly ash and Bhilai slag

Constituents	Fly ash (wt %)	Bhilai slag (wt %)
SiO ₂	57.48	35.50
Al ₂ O ₃	34.60	18.00
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.48	0.60
CaO	1.98	38.00
MgO	1.06	5.50
MnO	–	1.20
L.O.I. (at 900°)	1.20	1.53

Table 2. Batch composition of the fly ash and slag mixture (wt %)

Batch no.	Fly ash (wt %)	Slag (%)	Zircon flour (%)
I	50.0	50.0	0.0
II	45.0	45.0	10.0
III	42.5	42.5	15.0
IV	40.0	40.0	20.0

Fig. 1. Relation between fired bulk density and firing temperature of fly ash slag and zirconia based composites.

The magnitude of bulk density was higher than conventional aluminosilicate body due to incorporation of ZrO_2 . At all temperatures bulk density followed a direct relationship with ZrO_2 (Fig. 1). The nature of curves was identical irrespective of composition, each showing an inflection at 1250° beyond which the rate of increase was higher. Here, sintering was enhanced due to liquid formation as well as dissociation of zircon. Change of porosity with temperature in this type of combination is very much significant as it was always operated by two phenomena, i.e. generation of extra porosity by gas evolution and minimization of the porosity by material transport and

Fig. 2. Relation between % apparent porosity and firing temperature of fly ash slag and zirconia based composites.

growth. Rate of sintering was rapid. Porosity-temperature relationship (Fig. 2) was more sharp and the relationships were non-linear. Here dissociation of zircon was accelerated due to the presence of alkaline earth constituents. Apparent porosity decreased with zircon content and it may be noted

that particle packing in this type of uniaxially pressed compacts was not sufficient to minimize porosity. Initially slag offered the glassy phase. The reaction rate increase due to rapid dissociation of zircon in presence of CaO in the blast furnace slag.

The mechanical properties of a polycrystalline material are very much dependent on the inherent bond nature and also on the formed microstructure. The flexural strength of the composites fired at different temperatures was determined

Table 3. Flexural strength of the composites fired at different temperatures

Batch no.	Modulus of rupture (MPa) at different sintering temperature			
	1150°	1200°	1250°	1300°
I	25.5	36.1	40.1	54.1
II	42.5	45.2	51.2	75.0
III	47.5	51.2	57.2	82.0
IV	60.1	56.1	72.5	92.5

by three-point bending method and are given in the Table 3. Introduction of slag reduced the strength significantly and significant improvement was noticed with the incorporation of ZrO_2 . Maximum value was achieved at 1300° with 20% zircon. From the compositional nature of slag it is evident that it reduces the strength of the composite bodies due to formation of glass. Thus in Batch-I the flexural strength was minimum. Due to incorporation of ZrO_2 , the nature of the both glassy and crystalline phases changed which was reflected through the improvement of the flexural strength.

With the incorporation of ZrO_2 in the system true density increased. In the density-temperature curve, the inflection was noticed at 1250° which might be associated with the dissociation of zircon and development of particular polymorphic form of zirconia.

Identification of the crystalline phases was carried out by the X-ray analysis. The batch composition without zircon exhibited the presence of mullite as the major phase along with a trace amount of cristobalite. In other compositions with zircon, mullite formation was prominent along with generation of tetragonal zirconia, one of the desired phases in the toughened ceramics. Traces of unreacted zircon were noticed at higher zircon content in the batch.

The SEM micrographs (figures not shown) reveal that the texture is homogeneous and mullite formation starts with diffused grain boundary. After that, crystal growth is significant but that occurs in patches having irregular distribution of ZrO_2 . The glassy phase accumulates at the rim of the patches. At 1300° microstructure becomes

homogeneous and more compact. The grain boundary is very sharp and with the decrease in glass content needle growth is restricted. Rounded and sub-rounded zirconia particles are distributed throughout the matrix. Mostly intergranular zirconia is observed. The sizes of the latter ones are comparatively small. With further increase of temperature, disintegration of grains of both crystalline phase occurs with the formation of glassy phase causing dissolution and strain in the lattice.

Experimental

For preparing the composite, Chandrapura fly ash, Bhilai blast furnace slag and zircon flour were selected. They were mixed in proper proportion, ground and milled in a ball mill. The mixtures were lightly calcined, mixed with 0.1% polyvinyl alcohol as binder and subjected to uniaxial pressure of 1000 kg/cm². The dried shapes were sintered under slightly oxidizing condition at 1150–1350° for a fixed soaking period of 2 h.

A Philips PW 1790 X-ray diffractometer was used.

Measurement of the flexural strength was performed using Instron Universal 1185 testing machine, by three-point bending method. A Hitachi S415A scanning electron microscope was used.

The surface area was measured by BET method using Strohlein (Germany) workable at 230 V/50–60 Hz.

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